

CONCEPT AND FUNDAMENTALS OF LEGAL REGULATION OF INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL AGREEMENTS

Concept, Forms and Types of International Commercial Agreements

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Summary. The presented article reveals in detail the concept and foundations of the legal regulation of international commercial contracts, since they act as the main legal means of interaction between participants in commercial turnover. Through the conclusion of international commercial contracts, the essence and significance of international business activity is determined.

Key words: international commercial contracts, participants in civil transactions, entrepreneurial activity

The main legal means of interaction between participants in a commercial turnover is a civil contract. In the field of international commercial turnover, a civil law contract acquires the features of an international commercial contract. International commercial agreements mediate the international business activities of the parties and differ from similar internal transactions, as well as transactions that, although complicated by a foreign element, are concluded with the participation of the consumer¹.

In the science of international law, there is no unified definition of the concept of “international commercial agreement”. The historical development of the unification of the law of international commercial agreements, which began several centuries ago, encompasses the following stages. *The first stage* refers to the period of the emergence of medieval law as a law merchant, representing a set of international trade customs that regulated the political community of merchants who traveled from port to port and from fair to fair. *The second stage* was marked by the emergence of national legal systems under the influence of the understanding of law as a national phenomenon and the approval of the idea of national sovereignty. *The third stage*, the modern stage, was marked by a movement from national isolation to universal unification, which allowed, on the basis of multilateral negotiations, to develop and adopt uniform conflict of laws and substantive legal norms. It is to the third stage in the development of international legal unification of commercial law that the emergence of a uniform understanding of the category of international commercial agreements is assigned.

The first step on this path was *the 1955 Hague Convention on the Law Applicable to the International Sale of Goods*², Adopted within the framework of the Hague Conference on Private International Law. Although the parties to this convention were no more than ten states that belonged mainly to the Romano-Germanic system of law, it was this convention that had the largest number of parties among the universal international conventions on the unification of conflict of laws. Despite the fact that this convention did not offer a unified definition of an international commercial agreement, its significance lies in the recognition at the interstate level of the fact of the existence of an international sale of goods in accordance with Art. 1 of the Hague Convention. Analysis of the text of Art. 3 of the Hague Convention makes it possible to

¹ D.P. Strigunova, *Legal regulation of international commercial contracts*, Monograph. Moscow: YUSTITSINFORM, 2017, p. 178.

² 1955 Hague Convention on the Law Applicable to the International Sale of Goods. The Hague, 22.12.1986 (date of visit 29.06.2022). Available at: <https://docs.cntd.ru/document/901760972>.

indirectly assert that the concept of international sale and purchase within the meaning of the convention included those cases when the seller and the buyer were on the territory of different states.

The second step towards a uniform understanding of the category of “international commercial agreement” can be considered the adoption within the framework of UNIDROIT of two conventions: *the Hague Convention of 1964 on the Uniform Law on the International Sale of Goods*³ and *the Hague Convention of 1964 On the Uniform Law on the Conclusion of Contracts for the International Sale of Goods*⁴. Although both conventions, which had a small number of participating states, lost their effect due to the entry into force of the Vienna Convention, their significance consisted in the fact that they first introduced a legal definition of the concept of “international commercial agreement” (in the terminology of the conventions - an international agreement for sales of goods). In order for a commercial agreement to be recognized as international, it has to have two characteristics in the aggregate - one basic and one of the three additional ones. The main feature is that the main commercial enterprises of the counterparties – the seller and the buyer – are located on the territory of different states. An additional feature is that the following points are located on the territory of different states:

- the dispatch and destination of the goods sold, or
- making an offer and acceptance, or
- conclusion and execution of the contract.

It is quite obvious that a whole group of contracts related to the sale and purchase of goods at international exhibitions and having an indisputable international character, due to the above-mentioned requirements of the conventions, did not fall under the unified regime of legal regulation.

The most important step towards rectifying this situation can be considered *the Vienna Convention*⁵. According to paragraph (1) and paragraph (3) of Art. 1 of the Vienna Convention, the international character is inherent in those commercial contracts, the parties to which have their commercial enterprises on the territory of different states. Neither the nationality of the parties, nor their civil or commercial status, nor the civil or commercial nature of the contract are taken into account. Thus, **the modern understanding of the international nature of a trade agreement assumes that it has a commercial nature** (that is, it is concluded for business purposes, and not for the purpose of individual consumption) and **includes a foreign element** in the form of the location of the commercial enterprises of the seller and the buyer on the territory of different states.

Forms of International Commercial Agreements. There are *two forms of an international commercial agreement – oral and written*. The oral form assumes the presence of an oral agreement between the parties to conclude a contract. Written – provides for the fixation of the will of the parties on a material medium, which means the presence of both a single document signed by both counterparties, and messages transmitted by telegraph, telefax, teletype, etc. According to Art. 11 The Vienna Convention allows the conclusion of an international commercial contract

³ The Hague Convention of 1964 on the Uniform Law on the International Sale of Goods. The Hague, 01.07.1964 (date of visit 29.06.2022). Available at: https://studme.org/75895/pravo/konvencii_mezhdunarodnoy_kuple-_prodazhe_tovarov.

<https://www.alppp.ru/law/grazhdanskoe-pravo/mezhdunarodnoe-chastnoe-pravo/11/konvencija-o-edinoobraznom-zakone-o-zaklyuchenii-dogovorov-o-mezhdunarodnoj-dkuple--pro>.

⁴ The Hague Convention of 1964 On the Uniform Law on the Conclusion of Contracts for the International Sale of Goods. The Hague, 01.07.1964 (date of visit 29.06.2022). Available at: <https://www.alppp.ru/law/grazhdanskoe-pravo/mezhdunarodnoe-chastnoe-pravo/11/konvencija-o-edinoobraznom-zakone-o-zaklyuchenii-dogovorov-o-mezhdunarodnoj-dkuple.html>.

⁵ United Nations Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods. Vienna, 11 April 1980 (date visited 29.06.2022). Available: <http://www.cisg.ru/tekst-venskoj-konvencii-polnostyu.php>.

in any form, including orally. By virtue of this article, the fact of the conclusion of a contract can be proved by any means, including witness testimony. However, a very important exception has been made to this rule, taking into account the requirement of a mandatory written form in some national laws. In accordance with Art. 12 of the Vienna Convention, **a state party to the convention, whose legislation requires a mandatory written form of an international commercial contract, at any time can make a corresponding declaration.**

In this case, if at least one of the parties to the contract has its own commercial enterprise in the state that made such a declaration, **the provisions of the convention, which allow the use of not written, but any other form, will not apply to this contract.** Only in writing, in such a situation, both the contract itself or its termination by agreement of the parties, and an offer, acceptance or any other expression of intent should be performed. It should be noted that this is the only peremptory norm of the convention – all its other provisions are dispositive. The presence of this provision creates an opportunity for states to participate in the convention, the legislation of which imposes various requirements on the form of international commercial agreements.

Taking into account the civil legislation of the Republic of Moldova, the form of the transaction is subject to the law of the country, which is applicable to the transaction itself. However, the transaction cannot be invalidated due to non-compliance with the form, if the requirements of the law of the country – the place of the transaction to the form of the transaction – are met.

The development of scientific and technological progress and the expansion of the use of information and communication technologies in all spheres of society have generated the need for legal regulation of the form and procedure for concluding contracts using electronic means of communication. The efforts of the international community led to the development and adoption within the framework of UNCITRAL of *the New York UN Convention 2005 On the Use of Electronic Messages in International Contracts*⁶. The Convention **applies to the use of electronic communications in connection with the conclusion or performance of contracts between parties whose place of business is located in different states.** According to Art. 1 of this Convention, neither the nationality of the parties, nor their civil or commercial status, nor the civil or commercial nature of the contract, shall be taken into account in determining the applicability of this Convention. The Convention does not apply to electronic communications relating to:

- contracts concluded for personal, family or household purposes;
- transactions on the regulated stock market;
- transactions with foreign currency;
- interbank payment systems, interbank payment agreements or settlement and clearing systems for securities or other financial assets or instruments;
- to the transfer of security rights to securities, other financial assets and instruments held by the intermediary, to their sale, loan, possession or agreement to repurchase them.

Based on Art. 2 and Art. 3 The Convention does not apply to bills of exchange, promissory notes, bill of lading, warehouse receipts and any negotiable documents that give the beneficiary the right to demand delivery of goods or payment of a sum of money. The parties may exclude the application of this convention or derogate from any of its provisions or change its effect. Thus, the norms of the convention are given a dispositive character, which is consistent with the general principles of international commercial law.

With regard to the form of an international commercial agreement and any action aimed at concluding it, the convention contains a number of rules. So Art. 8 of the Convention provides that a message or a contract cannot be null and void just because it is in the form of **an electronic message**. Nothing in this convention requires a party to use or receive electronic communications, but its consent to do so may be inferred from that party's conduct. **Nothing in this**

⁶ New York UN Convention 2005 On the Use of Electronic Messages in International Contracts, dated November 23, 2005 (date of visit 29.06.2022). Available at: https://www.un.org/ru/documents/decl_conv/conventions/elect_com.shtml.

convention requires a communication or contract to be drawn up or confirmed in any particular form. In cases where the legislation requires that a message or contract be submitted in writing, or provides for the occurrence of certain consequences in the absence of a written form, this requirement is considered fulfilled by submitting an electronic message if the information contained therein is available for subsequent use in accordance with Art. 9 of the Convention.

Types of International Commercial Agreements

In determining the types and content of international commercial agreements, *the rules of interpretation of international trade terms INCOTERMS play an important role*⁷, which are by their legal nature an international trade custom. The first edition of INCOTERMS was adopted in 1936, the last one currently in force in 2010. In addition, there are several other editions of INCOTERMS, adopted between 1936 and 2010. This fact is explained by the fact that in international trade, under the influence of scientific and technological progress and informatization, new means and methods of delivering goods, processing documents, electronic means of transmitting information began to be used, which urgently required adjustments to the previously established standards and norms.

It should be noted that INCOTERMS are not themselves a source of international commercial law. The rules that make up their content are rules that have developed in international trade, which have acquired or are acquiring the quality of legal binding. ICC conducts only their generalization and adjustment for ease of use when concluding specific international commercial contracts. That is why the parties wishing to use INCOTERMS must make a special reference in the contract to the version of INCOTERMS, which they intend to follow. INCOTERMS-2010 contains detailed regulation of 11 types of contracts used in international trade. **The types of contracts** differ from each other in terms of basic terms. **Basic conditions** include:

- transportation of goods;
- goods insurance;
- the moment of transfer of ownership of the goods from the seller to the buyer;
- the moment of transfer of the risk of accidental loss and damage to the goods from the seller to the buyer;
- transfer of goods by the seller to the buyer.

The type of contract indicates how the scope of the rights and obligations of the seller and the buyer is determined in relation to the basic conditions. The Vienna Convention contains the most general description of the basic conditions, which boils down to the following.

With regard to **carriage and insurance**, the point is that, if the seller is obliged to ensure the carriage of the goods, he must conclude such contracts that are necessary for the carriage of the goods to the place of destination by means of transport appropriate under the given circumstances and under the conditions usual for such carriage. If the seller is not obliged to insure the goods during their transportation, he must, at the request of the buyer, provide him with all the information available for the implementation of such insurance by the buyer, in accordance with paragraph (2) and paragraph (3) of Art. 32 of the Convention.

With regard to **the transfer of goods** by the seller to the buyer, the requirements of the convention are that, unless the seller is obliged to deliver the goods at any other specified place, his obligation to deliver consists of:

- a) if the contract provides for the carriage of goods – in the delivery of the goods to the first carrier for transfer to the buyer;
- b) if, in cases not covered by the preceding sub-clause, the contract concerns goods defined by individual characteristics, or non-individualized goods, which must be taken from certain

⁷ International rules for the interpretation of trade terms INCOTERMS (date of visit 29.06.2022). Available at: <https://www.vladcargo.ru/info/directory-of-concepts-terms/international-rules-interpretation-terms-incoterms.html>.

stocks or manufactured or produced, and the parties at the time of the conclusion of the contract knew that the goods were or must be made or produced in a certain place,

c) in placing the goods at the disposal of the buyer at that place;

d) in other cases – in placing the goods at the disposal of the buyer in the place where at the time of the conclusion of the contract the seller's business was located, based on Art. 31 of the Convention.

With regard to **the transfer of the risk of accidental loss of or damage to the goods** from the seller to the buyer, the convention contains a special chapter IV "Transfer of risk". The legal consequences of the transfer of risk are that the loss or damage to the goods after the risk has passed to the buyer does not release him from the obligation to pay the price, unless the loss or damage was caused by the actions or omissions of the seller, in accordance with Art. 66 of the Convention. If the contract provides for the carriage of the goods and the seller is not obligated to hand them over at any specific location, the risk passes to the buyer when the goods are handed over to the first carrier for transfer to the buyer in accordance with the contract. If the seller is obliged to hand over the goods to the carrier at a specific location, the risk does not pass to the buyer until the goods have been handed over to the carrier at that location. The fact that the seller is authorized to withhold the title deeds does not affect the transfer of risk. However, the risk does not pass to the buyer until the goods are clearly identified for the purposes of this contract by marking, by means of shipping documents, as well as by notification sent to the buyer or otherwise, based on Art. 67 of the Convention.

There are no provisions on the moment of transfer of ownership of the goods from the seller to the buyer in the convention. In this case, the applicable national law applies, which generally takes *two approaches* to this issue, based on consensual and traditional systems. According to **the consensual system**, ownership is transferred to individually defined things at the time of the conclusion of the contract, and to things defined by generic characteristics, at the time of their individualization, i.e. transfer. **The traditional system** associates the transfer of ownership of any things with their transfer by the alienator to the acquirer. The transfer of ownership usually coincides with the transfer to the acquirer of the risk of accidental loss or damage to the goods. However, these moments do not always coincide.

In INCOTERMS 2010, *two groups of types of contracts* can be distinguished, associated both with transportation by any mode of transport (including combined), and with transportation by sea and inland water transport. When concluding a foreign economic contract, the issue of transfer of ownership must be specially stipulated in the contract⁸. The various types of international commercial contracts can be summarized in Table 1.

This classification is based on one principle: one or another type of international commercial contract is applied depending on the mode of transport by which the goods are transported. The first group covers seven types of contracts providing for the carriage of goods by any mode of transport. The second group includes four types of contracts in which the carriage of goods is carried out by sea and inland waterway transport. The first letter of the contract type code is deciphered as follows.

E – shipment. The seller is obliged to deliver the goods to the buyer directly at the manufacturing plant.

F – the main carriage is not paid by the seller. The seller undertakes to place the goods at the disposal of the carrier hired by the buyer.

C – the main carriage was paid by the seller. The seller must conclude a contract for the carriage of the goods, but without assuming the risk of accidental loss or damage.

D – arrival. The seller bears all costs and assumes all risks until the goods are delivered to the country of destination⁹.

⁸ E.Z. Sevostyanenko, G.V. Perepelitsa, V.I. Perepelitsa, E.V. Chevigalov, *Fundamentals of International Trade: A Guide for Beginner Experts*, Donetsk, 2015, p. 9.

⁹ V.F. Popondopulo, *International commercial law. A text book for masters*, Moscow: Yurayt, 2017,

Кодовое обозначение типа контракта	Название типа контракта	
	на английском языке	на русском языке
Типы контрактов, применяемых при перевозках товаров любым видом транспорта		
EXW	Ex Works	Франко завод
FCA	Free Carrier	Франко перевозчик
CPT	Carriage Paid to	Перевозка оплачена до ...
CIP	Carriage and Insurance Paid to	Перевозка и страхование оплачены до ...
DAT	Delivered at Terminal	Поставлено на терминале
DAP	Delivered at Place	Поставлено в согласованном месте
DDP	Delivered Duty Paid	Поставлено с оплатой пошлин
Типы контрактов, применяемых при перевозках товаров морским и внутренним водным транспортом		
FAS	Free Alongside Ship	Свободно вдоль борта судна
FOB	Free on Board	Свободно на борту
CFR	Cost and Freight	Стоимость и фрахт
CIF	Cost, Insurance and Freight	Стоимость, страхование и фрахт

Table 1

Understanding the meaning of the first letter in the code designation of the type of contract allows you to see **the sequential increase in the scope of the seller's obligations in relation to the basic conditions**. From this point of view, contracts such as EXW and DDP occupy positions that are polar opposite to each other. The EXW type contract stipulates the minimum scope of the seller's obligations, which must provide the goods in a properly packed form at the disposal of the buyer at the manufacturer's plant. All other operations for the transportation of goods, insurance, customs clearance are the responsibility of the buyer. As a result, the price of an EXW type contract is the lowest. The exact opposite is the DDP-type contract, in which the scope of the seller's responsibilities is set to the maximum. The seller is obliged not only to carry out customs clearance of the goods, having paid both export and import duties, but also to insure the goods, as well as to ensure their delivery to the point of destination in the territory of the buyer's state. Obviously, the contract price in this case will be the highest, since the seller will try to take into account all his costs when calculating the price. Let us dwell in more detail on the characteristics of certain types of international commercial contracts.

1. Contract Type "Ex Works (specified location)". "Ex Works" means that the seller is deemed to have fulfilled his obligations to supply the goods when he has placed the goods at the disposal of the buyer directly on his territory (for example, a factory, a factory, a warehouse, etc.). The seller is not responsible for loading the goods onto a vehicle provided by the buyer and for clearing the goods for export unless otherwise agreed. The buyer bears all types of risks and all costs of moving the goods from the seller's premises to the desired destination. Thus, this type of contract provides for a minimum obligation for the seller. This contract should not be used when the buyer is unable, directly or indirectly, to comply with export formalities. In these cases, one should resort to the "free carrier" type. The type of contract "Ex Works" can be used for transportation by any means of transport¹⁰.

p. 165.

¹⁰ E.V. Trunina, Yu.V. Fedasova, *Commercial law. Textbook*, Moscow: Yurayt, 2009, p. 205.

2. Contract Type “Free Carrier (indicated place)”. “Free carrier” means that the seller is deemed to have fulfilled his obligation to deliver the goods when he handed over the goods cleared for export to the carrier chosen by the buyer at the named place or point. If the exact point is not specified by the buyer, the seller himself can choose a place within the designated territory for transferring the goods to the carrier. The operations of loading the goods are assigned to the seller. Where commercial practice requires the seller to cooperate with the carrier (for example, in rail or air transport), the seller may act at the buyer’s risk and expense. **A carrier** is any person who, under a contract of carriage, has undertaken to carry out carriage by rail, road, sea, air, river transport or a combination of these types of transport. If the buyer instructs the seller to hand over the goods to a person, such as a freight forwarder, who is not the carrier, the seller is deemed to have fulfilled his delivery obligations when the goods have been handed over to that person. **A container** is understood as any equipment that serves to unify cargo, for example, all types of containers or wagons – platforms of international and other standards, trailers, exchange containers, equipment related to any type of transport. This type of contract can be used for transportation by any means of transport, including multimodal transport.

3. Contract Type “Carriage Paid to (named place of destination)”. “Carriage Paid To” means that the seller pays the freight for the carriage of the goods to the named place of destination. The risk of loss of or damage to the goods, as well as any additional costs incurred after the delivery of the goods to the carrier, passes from the seller to the buyer, placing the goods at the disposal of the carrier. In the case of transportation to the specified destination by several carriers, the risk passes at the time the goods are handed over to the first carrier. Carriage Paid To requires the seller to clear the goods for export. This type of contract can be used for transportation by any means of transport.

4. Contract type “Carriage and Insurance Paid to (named place of destination)”. “Carriage and insurance paid to” means that the seller has the same obligations as for carriage paid to, but with the addition that he is obliged to insure the goods against loss or damage during carriage. The seller enters into an insurance contract and pays the insurance premium. The buyer should be aware that on a “carriage and insurance paid to” basis, the seller is only required to provide insurance for the minimum amount of liability. Under the conditions of “carriage and insurance paid to”, the seller is obliged to clear the goods for export. This type of contract can be used for transportation by any means of transport¹¹.

5. Contract Type “Delivered at Terminal (specified terminal)”. “Delivered at the terminal” means that the seller has fulfilled his delivery obligations when the goods, unloaded from the arriving vehicle, are placed at the disposal of the buyer at the agreed place of destination. “Terminal” includes any place such as a quay, warehouse, warehouse restaurant yard, automobile, railway or air terminal. The seller shall bear all costs and all risk of transporting the goods (except for duties, taxes and other official charges levied when importing) to the named place and unloading it at the terminal. If the seller fails to clear customs on time for export, any additional costs and risk involved shall be the buyer’s responsibility. The seller is not required to comply with import customs formalities and pay import duties. If the parties agree to impose on the seller the risks and costs of transportation and movement of goods from the terminal to another location, it is advisable to resort to DAP and DDP contracts. The delivered at the terminal type can be used for transportation by any means of transport.

6. Contract Type “Delivered at the Agreed Place (indicated agreed place)”. “Delivered at the agreed place” means that the seller is deemed to have fulfilled his delivery obligations when he has placed the goods at the disposal of the buyer in an arriving vehicle ready for unloading at the agreed place of destination. The seller is responsible for all costs and risks of transporting the goods (excluding duties, taxes and other official fees charged when importing) to the named place. If the seller fails to clear customs on time for export, any additional costs and risk

¹¹ Yu.E. Bulatetsky, I.M. Rassolov, *Trade (commercial) law*, Moscow: Yurayt, 2014, p. 216.

involved shall be the buyer's responsibility. If the parties agree that the customs formalities, as well as the associated costs and risks, are borne by the seller, then this should be duly reflected in the wording of this type of contract. If the parties agree to entrust the seller with the customs formalities for import, payment of any import duties, it is advisable to use the DDP type of contract. The type "delivered at an agreed place" can be used for transportation by any means of transport¹².

7. Contract type "Delivered Duty Paid (named place of destination)". "Delivered duty paid" means that the seller has met his delivery obligations when he has delivered the goods at the named place in the importing country. The seller is at the risk and expense of shipping the item, including duties, taxes and other official charges, and customs clearance of the item for import. If the type "ex works" implies a minimum of obligations for the seller, then the type "delivered with payment of duty" – the maximum obligations. This type should not be used if the seller is unable, directly or indirectly, to obtain an import license. If the parties wish the buyer to clear the import and pay the duty, a different type of contract, such as DAP, should be used. Any taxes payable upon import are at the expense of the seller, unless otherwise expressly agreed in an international commercial contract. This type of contract can be used for transportation by any means of transport.

8. Contract type "Free Along the Side of the Vessel (specified port of shipment)". "Free alongside the ship" means that the seller is deemed to have met his obligation to deliver the goods when the goods are placed alongside the ship on the quay or on a barge at the named port of shipment. Thus, the buyer bears all costs and risk of loss or damage to the goods from that moment on. The seller fulfills his obligation to deliver when he hands over the goods to the carrier and not when the goods have reached their destination. When placing goods in containers, it is typical for the seller to hand over the goods to the carrier at the terminal rather than by placing them alongside the ship. In such situations, the contract type FCA should be used. The "free alongside ship" type requires the seller to clear the goods for export. This type of contract can only be used for sea or river transport¹³.

9. Contract type "Free on Board (designated port of shipment)". "Free on board" means that the seller is deemed to have met his obligation to deliver the goods when the goods are delivered on board the ship at the named port of shipment. Therefore, the buyer must bear all costs and risk of loss or damage to the goods from that point onwards. The free on board type requires the seller to clear the goods for export. The seller fulfills his obligation to deliver when he hands over the goods to the carrier and not when the goods have reached their destination. When placing goods in containers, it is typical for the seller to hand over the goods to the carrier at the terminal rather than by placing them on board the ship. In such situations, the CPT contract type should be used. The free on board type can only be used for sea or river transport.

10. Contract type "Cost and Freight (specified port of destination)". "Cost and freight" means that the seller bears the costs and freight necessary to deliver the goods to the specified port of destination. In this case, the risk of loss or damage to the goods, as well as any additional costs due to events occurring after the delivery of the goods on board the ship, passes from the seller to the buyer at the time the goods are on board the ship at the specified port of shipment. The cost and freight type requires the seller to clear the goods for export. The seller fulfills his obligation to deliver when he hands over the goods to the carrier and not when the goods have reached their destination. When placing goods in containers, it is typical for the seller to hand over the goods to the carrier at the terminal rather than by placing them on board the ship. In such situations, the CPT contract type should be used. The cost and freight type can only be used for sea or river transport.

11. Contract type "Cost, Insurance and Freight (specified port of destination)". "Cost, insurance and freight" means that the seller has the same obligations as under the terms "cost

¹² T.A. Batrova, *Commercial law*, Moscow: Norma, 2005, p. 105.

¹³ L.A. Lunts, *Private International Law Course*, Moscow: Spark, 2002, p. 467.

and freight”, but with the addition that he is obliged to provide marine insurance of the cargo against its loss or damage. The seller enters into an insurance contract and pays the insurance premium. The buyer should be aware that on a cost, insurance and freight basis, the seller is only required to provide insurance for the minimum amount of liability. The cost, insurance and freight type requires the seller to clear the goods for export. The seller fulfills his obligation to deliver when he hands over the goods to the carrier and not when the goods have reached their destination. When placing goods in containers, it is typical for the seller to hand over the goods to the carrier at the terminal rather than by placing them on board the ship. In such situations, the CIP contract type should be used. The type “cost, insurance and freight” can only be used for sea or river transportation¹⁴. Do not forget that the unlimited number of contracts devoid of legal consolidation is not an indicator of productive regulation of various kinds of joint relations, but only a clearly built system of chain links of certain types of contracts, where their legal regulation will give an effective result in regulating various kinds of relations. For this, such a principle as freedom of contract was envisaged, representing the freedom to conclude various types of contractual structures regulating public relations that meet the needs of society¹⁵.

¹⁴ G.K. Dmitrieva, *International Private Law*, Moscow: Prospect, 2016, p. 175.

¹⁵ O. Tatar, *Unnamed Contracts as a Means of Updating the Contractual System of the Republic of Moldova*, Monograph, Comrat: Typ. “A&V Poligraf”, 2021, p. 20.